

Basti Therapy: Regulating Vata Dosha for a Healthy Pregnancy

Dr.Shikha Singh

Asst. Professor, Dept. of Prasuti Tantra, Faculty of Ayurveda
IMS, BHU

Corresponding Author: Dr.Shikha Singh

ABSTRACT:

Pregnancy heralds a natural increase in Kapha dosha due to factors such as nourishment augmentation (Rasa vriddhi) and Kapha-promoting dietary and lifestyle habits. Even slight modifications in lifestyle can disrupt doshic equilibrium. Factors like dietary habits favoring Vata aggravation, disrupted sleep patterns (common during pregnancy), seasonal changes, reduced food intake, and vomiting contribute to Vata dosha vitiation. Imbalanced Vata dosha serves as a primary instigator for various physical and psychological anomalies in pregnant women, including conditions like PROM (Premature Rupture of Membranes) and IUGR (Intrauterine Growth Restriction). Hence, it becomes imperative to maintain Vata in a balanced state. Basti therapy emerges as a paramount intervention for regulating Vata dosha, which governs a multitude of physiological and pathological processes within the body and mind. Typically, Panchakarma therapies, including Basti, are contraindicated during pregnancy. However, certain specific types of Basti suitable for pregnancy are elucidated in this discourse.

Keywords: Basti, Pregnancy, Vata dosha

1. INTRODUCTION:

The term "Basti" finds its roots in Sanskrit, derived from the root "vas" with the addition of the "tich" pratyaya, classified as masculine gender according to Vachaspatyam. The root "vas" signifies "nivas," meaning to reside, stay, or dwell, also encompassing the idea of covering or coating. In the context of Basti therapy, it refers to the coating of sneha (oil or ghee) for elimination. Literally translating to bag, container, or bladder, "Basti" originally denoted the use of sterilized urinary bladders from animals for administering enemas, hence its name as Basti Karma. In modern practice, plastic enema equipment and syringes are utilized to deliver medicated decoctions, including medicated oil or cleansing solutions, into the patient's intestines. "Basti" stands as the primary treatment for disorders related to "vata" according to Ayurvedic principles. Acharya Charak emphasized the paramount importance of addressing "vata" imbalances, stating that no cause is greater than "vata" in the manifestation of disease, and no remedy surpasses the efficacy of Basti therapy.[1]

Basti therapy holds the remarkable ability to alleviate diseases stemming from all three doshas (tridoshas). By penetrating the moola sthana (root site) of vata, which is considered the origin of many ailments, Basti has the potential to thoroughly eradicate vitiated doshas. As such, it is often regarded as half or even the entirety of the treatment regimen. Its comprehensive approach in addressing doshic imbalances underscores its significance as a cornerstone therapy in Ayurveda.[2]

During pregnancy, a natural increase in Kapha dosha occurs due to dietary and lifestyle factors such as increased nourishment intake (Rasa vriddhi) and Kapha-promoting habits. Even minor alterations in diet and lifestyle can influence the doshic balance. Conversely, factors like dietary practices and lifestyle habits favoring Vata aggravation, sleep disturbances (common during pregnancy), seasonal changes, reduced food intake, and vomiting can lead to the vitiation of Vata dosha.

The vitiated Vata dosha emerges as a primary contributor to numerous physical and psychological abnormalities in pregnant women. Elevated Vata dosha levels have been linked to conditions like preterm delivery, premature rupture of membranes, low birth weight, and intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). Additionally, it impacts the psychological well-being of pregnant women, with decreased Satva (clarity and harmony) and increased Raja (activity) and Tama (inertia).

An increase in Raja may manifest as anxiety, fear, and reduced pain tolerance, while heightened Tama can result in depression, negative thoughts, fear of delivery, and reduced pain tolerance, potentially leading to decreased cooperation during labor and an increased likelihood of operative delivery. Moreover, the risk of postpartum depression is heightened in such cases.

Given these implications, it becomes imperative to maintain Vata dosha in a balanced state during pregnancy. Basti therapy emerges as an optimal intervention for regulating Vata dosha, considering its role as the chief governing factor behind physiological and pathological processes in both the body and mind.

Material and Methods: All Samhitas were searched for Basti during pregnancy and analyzed.

2. TYPES OF BASTI GIVEN DURING PREGNANCY:-

2.1 Anuvasana (oil enema): Basti therapy employing medicated oils, tonics, and herbal milk is specifically indicated for pure Vata disorders and individuals experiencing symptoms of excess hunger or dryness associated with Vata imbalances. This therapeutic approach aims to pacify aggravated Vata dosha and restore balance to the body. By administering nourishing and soothing substances through Basti, it helps alleviate symptoms such as excessive hunger or dryness while addressing the underlying Vata imbalance. This targeted treatment can effectively bring relief and promote overall well-being in individuals with Vata-related conditions.

2.2 Niruha-Asthapana (decoction enema): Basti therapy, utilizing water-based medical extracts or medicated water, serves as a versatile and potent treatment modality for a myriad of health conditions. Its efficacy spans across diverse ailments, including gastrointestinal disturbances, nervous system disorders, and urinary irregularities. By harnessing the therapeutic potential of water-based medicaments, Basti facilitates the expulsion of excess Vata dosha from the body, offering relief from symptoms such as abdominal discomfort, tremors, and irregular bowel movements. Additionally, Basti proves beneficial in managing conditions like gout, fever, and unconsciousness, aiding in toxin elimination, immune support, and consciousness restoration, respectively.

Moreover, this ancient Ayurvedic therapy extends its healing touch to alleviate pain, improve appetite, and mitigate hyperacidity, contributing to overall wellness and vitality. Basti's holistic approach addresses not only the physical manifestations of illness but also supports emotional and mental well-being by promoting relaxation and balance. Its application in heart diseases underscores its role in enhancing cardiovascular health and circulation, thus aiding in the management of cardiac conditions. In essence, Basti therapy with water-based medicaments

stands as a cornerstone of Ayurvedic medicine, offering a gentle yet profound path to restoration and rejuvenation.

2.3 Matra Basti (daily oil enema): Basti therapy emerges as a boon for individuals depleted by overexertion, excessive physical activity, or chronic Vata disorders. Whether it's the result of strenuous work, heavy lifting, prolonged walking, or excessive sexual activity, Basti offers a rejuvenating solution. This therapeutic intervention doesn't necessitate stringent dietary restrictions or daily routines, making it accessible and adaptable for various lifestyles. Additionally, its application isn't bound by seasonal limitations, rendering it effective year-round.

By harnessing the power of Basti, individuals experiencing depletion find renewed strength and vitality. It aids in replenishing the body, promoting healthy weight gain, and facilitating the elimination of waste products. Basti serves as a holistic approach to wellness, addressing not only physical exhaustion but also fostering a sense of balance and rejuvenation. Its versatility and effectiveness make it a valuable tool in the arsenal of Ayurvedic therapies, offering respite and restoration to those in need.

2.4 Brihana Basti (nutritional enema): Basti therapy is employed to offer profound nourishment in specific conditions, utilizing traditionally rich and nutritive substances. Among these, warm milk, meat broth, bone marrow soup, and esteemed herbs such as shatavari, ashwagandha, yashtimadhu, or vidarikanda are commonly utilized. This therapeutic approach aims to deeply nurture the body, providing essential nutrients and rejuvenating elements to support healing and overall well-being. By incorporating these highly nutritive substances, Basti therapy enhances vitality, strengthens the body, and promotes optimal health. Its utilization of natural, nourishing ingredients underscores its efficacy as a holistic means of addressing health concerns and fostering vitality.

3. BASTI GIVEN DURING PREGNANCY:

Typically, both Basti therapy and other Panchakarma procedures are contraindicated during pregnancy due to the potential risks involved. However, there are a few specific types of Basti that can be administered safely during pregnancy. These specialized Basti treatments are carefully selected to ensure the well-being of both the mother and the unborn child while addressing specific health concerns that may arise during pregnancy. It's essential for pregnant individuals to consult with a qualified Ayurvedic practitioner who can provide guidance on safe and appropriate treatments tailored to their unique needs and circumstances.

4. BASTI IN 5TH MONTH:

During the fifth month of pregnancy, Asthapan and Anuvasanbasti are typically administered to address specific diseases or conditions in pregnant women. However, it's important to note that basti treatments are generally avoided before the fifth month of pregnancy. This precaution is due to the fact that during the first trimester, the uterus is considered a pelvic organ, and the administration of basti treatments could potentially cause trauma to the uterus, increasing the risk of abortion.[3]

After the fourth month of pregnancy, basti treatments may be considered if deemed necessary and appropriate for the individual's health condition. However, caution should always be exercised, and any decision to proceed with basti therapy during pregnancy should be made under the guidance of a qualified Ayurvedic practitioner who can assess the risks and benefits on a case-by-case basis to ensure the safety and well-being of both the mother and the unborn child.

4.1 Niruha Basti, Consisting Of Sour And Salty Drugs, Is Formulated With Specific Therapeutic Actions In Mind[3]:

1. Sour Drugs: These components possess properties aimed at pacifying Vata and Kapha doshas. They work to alleviate imbalances associated with these doshas, which are characterized by qualities such as dryness, coldness, and instability. Sour drugs help to bring about stability and grounding, promoting a sense of balance within the body.
2. Salty Drugs: Similarly, the salty drugs included in Niruha Basti also serve to pacify Vata and Kapha doshas. They work synergistically with the sour drugs to further mitigate the effects of these doshic imbalances. Salty substances have grounding and nourishing properties, helping to restore equilibrium and harmony to the body.

Overall, Niruha Basti containing sour and salty drugs is categorized as a Vata-Kapha Shamak Basti. This designation indicates its primary therapeutic action of pacifying both Vata and Kapha doshas, making it particularly beneficial for conditions characterized by the imbalance of these doshas. Through its targeted effects, this type of Basti aims to restore doshic equilibrium and promote overall health and well-being.

4.2 Anuvasana Basti, Also Known As Sneha Basti, Comprises Medicated Oil Infused With Sweet Drugs. The Ingredients And Their Actions In This Type Of Basti Are As Follows:

1. Sweet Drugs: The sweet drugs utilized in Anuvasana Basti are chosen for their ability to pacify Vata and Pitta doshas. These substances possess qualities that help to alleviate imbalances associated with these doshas, such as dryness, heat, and excess mobility. Sweet drugs work to promote nourishment, lubrication, and stability within the body.

As a result, Anuvasana Basti is categorized as a Vata-Pitta Shamak Basti. This designation indicates its primary therapeutic action of pacifying both Vata and Pitta doshas, making it particularly beneficial for conditions characterized by the imbalance of these doshas. Through its targeted effects, Anuvasana Basti aims to restore doshic equilibrium and promote overall health and well-being.

5. BASTI IN 8TH MONTH:

During the eighth month of pregnancy, Anuvasan and Asthapanbasti treatments are often administered using medications primarily aimed at pacifying Kapha and Vata doshas. At this stage of pregnancy, hormonal changes and an increase in Kapha and Vata doshas may lead to common issues such as constipation and backache.

The therapeutic action of these basti treatments, which are specifically tailored to address Kapha-Vata imbalances, helps regulate Vata dosha while also providing strength to the pregnant woman in preparation for delivery. By targeting these doshic imbalances, Anuvasan and Asthapanbasti treatments can alleviate symptoms like constipation and backache, promoting overall comfort and well-being for the expectant mother as she approaches childbirth.

It's important to note that these basti treatments should be administered under the guidance of a qualified Ayurvedic practitioner to ensure their safety and effectiveness for the pregnant woman and her baby.

In the eighth month of pregnancy, **an Asthapan Basti is commonly administered. This particular Basti formulation includes a decoction of Badar mixed with Bala, Atibala, Shatapushpa, Palal, milk, curd, oil, salt, Madanphala, honey, and ghrita. Here's an analysis of the contents and their therapeutic actions:[4]**

1. Badar: Possesses Kapha-Vata shamak properties, aiming to pacify both Kapha and Vata doshas.

2. Bala and Atibala: Both herbs have Vata-Pitta shamak qualities, aiding in the alleviation of imbalances related to Vata and Pitta doshas.
3. Shatapushpa: Known for its Kapha-Vata shamak properties, it helps balance both Kapha and Vata doshas.
4. Palal: Exhibits Vata shamak actions, targeting the pacification of Vata dosha.
5. Madanphala: Possesses Kapha-Vata shamak properties, helping to balance both Kapha and Vata doshas.

Given the predominant actions of the ingredients involved, this Basti formulation primarily aims to pacify Vata and Kapha doshas. By addressing imbalances in these doshas, the Asthapan Basti helps provide relief from symptoms commonly experienced during the eighth month of pregnancy, such as constipation and backache, while also preparing the pregnant woman for childbirth. However, it's crucial to ensure that this treatment is administered under the guidance of a qualified Ayurvedic practitioner to ensure its safety and effectiveness for the expectant mother and her baby.

5.1 Anuvasan Basti Administered With Oil Medicated With Milk And Decoction Of 'Madhur Group Drugs' Primarily Exhibits Vata-Pitta Shamak Properties. Here's An Analysis Of The Contents And Their Therapeutic Actions:[4]

1. Milk: Milk is known for its Vata-Pitta shamak properties. It possesses qualities that help alleviate imbalances related to both Vata and Pitta doshas, promoting soothing and cooling effects on the body.
2. Drugs of Madhura Group: The drugs belonging to the madhura group also exhibit Vata-Pitta shamak actions. These substances are selected for their ability to pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas, contributing to the overall balancing effect of the Anuvasan Basti.

Given the predominant actions of the ingredients involved, this particular Anuvasan Basti formulation serves to pacify Vata and Pitta doshas. By addressing imbalances in these doshas, it helps alleviate symptoms associated with conditions related to Vata and Pitta, promoting balance and harmony within the body. However, it's important to ensure that this treatment is administered under the guidance of a qualified Ayurvedic practitioner to ensure its safety and effectiveness for the individual's specific health needs.

5.2 In the case of the Niruha Basti given with a decoction of Badar mixed with Palal, milk, Dadhimastu, oil, salt, Madanphala, ghrita, and honey, the therapeutic actions can be analyzed as follows:[5]

1. Badar: Known for its Kapha-Vata shamak properties, Badar helps pacify both Kapha and Vata doshas, thereby reducing their imbalances in the body.
2. Palal: Exhibiting Vata shamak actions, Palal specifically targets the pacification of the Vata dosha, helping to alleviate symptoms associated with Vata imbalances.
3. Madanphala: Possessing Kapha-Vata shamak properties, Madanphala contributes to the balancing of both Kapha and Vata doshas, aiding in the reduction of their aggravation.

Given the predominant actions of the ingredients involved, this Niruha Basti formulation is categorized as a Vata-Kapha shamakbasti. It primarily aims to pacify both Vata and Kapha doshas, making it beneficial for conditions associated with the imbalances of these doshas. By addressing these doshic imbalances, the Niruha Basti helps restore equilibrium to the body and promotes overall well-being. However, it's important to ensure that this treatment is administered under the guidance of a qualified Ayurvedic practitioner to ensure its safety and effectiveness for the individual's specific health needs.

5.3 In the case of the Anuvasan Basti formulated with oil medicated with decoction of Madhuk and other madhur drugs, the therapeutic actions can be summarized as follows:[5]

Madhuk: Exhibiting Vata-Pitta shamak properties, Madhuk helps pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas, thereby reducing their imbalances in the body.

Given that Madhuk primarily acts as a Vata-Pitta shamak, this Anuvasan Basti formulation can be classified as a Vata-Pitta shamakbasti. It aims to pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas, making it beneficial for conditions associated with the imbalances of these doshas. By addressing these doshic imbalances, the Anuvasan Basti helps restore equilibrium to the body and promotes overall well-being. However, as with any Ayurvedic treatment, it's important to ensure that this therapy is administered under the guidance of a qualified Ayurvedic practitioner to ensure its safety and effectiveness for the individual's specific health needs.

5.4 Anuvasan Basti administered with ghrita medicated with madhura drugs combines the therapeutic actions of both the ghrita and the madhura drugs. Here's an analysis of the contents and their actions:[6]

Madhura Drugs: These substances possess Vata-Pitta shamak properties, meaning they pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas. They help alleviate symptoms and imbalances associated with these doshas, promoting balance and harmony in the body.

Ghrita: Ghrita, or medicated ghee, also exhibits Vata-Pitta shamak actions. It aids in pacifying both Vata and Pitta doshas, contributing to the overall balancing effect of the Anuvasan Basti.

Given that both the madhura drugs and ghrita possess Vata-Pitta shamak properties, this Anuvasan Basti formulation is categorized as a Vata-Pitta shamakbasti. It primarily aims to pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas, making it beneficial for conditions associated with the imbalances of these doshas. By addressing these doshic imbalances, the Anuvasan Basti helps restore equilibrium to the body and promotes overall well-being. However, as always, it's important to ensure that this treatment is administered under the guidance of a qualified Ayurvedic practitioner to ensure its safety and effectiveness for the individual's specific health needs.

5.5 In the Niruha Basti formulation consisting of a decoction of Shushkamulak, kola, and amla dravya mixed with Shatapushpakalka, oil, ghrita, and salt, the therapeutic actions can be understood through the analysis of the contents:[7]

1. Shushkamulak and Kola: Both of these ingredients exhibit Kapha-Vata shamak properties, meaning they pacify both Kapha and Vata doshas. They help alleviate symptoms and imbalances associated with these doshas, promoting balance and harmony in the body.
2. Shatapushpa: Shatapushpa also possesses Kapha-Vata shamak properties, contributing to the overall balancing effect of the Niruha Basti. It aids in pacifying both Kapha and Vata doshas.
3. Amla dravya: Amla dravya has Vata shamak actions, targeting the pacification of the Vata dosha. It helps alleviate symptoms and imbalances associated with Vata dosha, promoting stability and grounding in the body.

Given the predominant actions of the ingredients involved, this Niruha Basti formulation is categorized as a Kapha-Vata shamakbasti. It primarily aims to pacify both Kapha and Vata doshas, making it beneficial for conditions associated with the imbalances of these doshas. By addressing these doshic imbalances, the Niruha Basti helps restore equilibrium to the body and promotes overall well-being. However, as always, it's important to ensure that this treatment is

administered under the guidance of a qualified Ayurvedic practitioner to ensure its safety and effectiveness for the individual's specific health needs.

6.BASTI IN 9TH MONTH:

In the ninth month, administering Anuvasanbasti provides women with strength and eases tension in the pelvic bones, aiding in labor preparation.

6.1 The Anuvasanbasti, infused with oil medicated with sweet (madhura) herbs, serves a dual purpose:[8]

- The sweet herbs pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas.
- Hence, it functions as a Vata-Pitta shamakbasti.

6.2 Administering Anuvasanbasti with oil medicated with Kadamb and Masha presents a comprehensive approach to balancing the doshas, or energies, within the body:[9]

1. **Kadamb:** This herb is renowned for its ability to pacify all three doshas - Vata, Pitta, and Kapha. It possesses properties that help in harmonizing the imbalances of these doshas. By incorporating Kadamb into the basti oil, it ensures a holistic approach towards dosha equilibrium.
2. **Masha:** Masha, also known as black gram, is particularly effective in pacifying Vata dosha. Vata dosha, being responsible for movement and communication within the body, can become aggravated due to various factors such as stress, improper diet, or lifestyle choices. By including Masha in the basti oil, it specifically targets the pacification of Vata dosha, thereby addressing any related imbalances.

By combining Kadamb and Masha in the Anuvasanbasti oil, the treatment becomes multifaceted. It not only balances all three doshas but also pays specific attention to calming the aggravated Vata dosha. This comprehensive approach ensures that the basti therapy is effective in addressing a wide range of imbalances and promoting overall well-being.

7.BASTI IN UDAVARTA:

Udavarta, derived from "Uta" meaning upward and "Avarta" meaning direction, refers to the movement of Vata dosha in an upward direction within the body. Typically, Vata governs movement in a downward direction, but when it moves upward, it leads to a condition known as Udavarta. This reversal of Vata's natural course can result in various digestive issues, including constipation.

To address Udavarta and associated constipation, specific basti treatments are administered. These bastis are designed to regulate the function of Vata, particularly the "Apana Vayu," which governs downward movement and elimination in the body. Additionally, these bastis aim to enhance "Pachakagni," the digestive fire responsible for digestion and metabolism.

By regulating Apana Vayu and increasing Pachakagni, these basti treatments effectively manage Udavarta. They help in restoring the natural downward movement of Vata and promote proper digestion and elimination, thereby alleviating constipation and associated symptoms.

In summary, Udavarta is addressed through basti treatments that focus on regulating Apana Vayu and increasing Pachakagni, ultimately restoring balance to the digestive system and treating the condition effectively.

7.1 The Asthanbasti Is Composed Of A Decoction Made From Various Roots And Herbs, Combined With Additional Ingredients To Enhance Its Therapeutic Effects. Here's A Breakdown Of The Components:[10]

1. **Decoction Of Roots:**
 - Viran

- Shali
 - Shashtik
 - Kush
 - Kash
 - Ikshubalika
 - Vetas
 - Jalavetas
2. **Additional Herbs:**
- Bhootika
 - Anantamula
 - Kashmari
 - Parushak
 - Madhuk
 - Mridwik
3. **Liquid Medium:**
- Milk: Provides nourishment and supports the action of the herbs.
4. **Other Ingredients:**
- Priyal
 - Vibhitak-majja
 - Tilakalka
 - Salt: Used for its preservative and balancing properties.
- **Viran:** Pacifies Kapha and Pitta doshas.
 - **Shali, Shashtik, Kush:** All three herbs pacify all three doshas, making them Tridoshshamak.
 - **Kash, Ikshubalika:** Pacify Vata and Pitta doshas.
 - **Vetas, Jalavetas:** Pacify Kapha and Pitta doshas.
 - **Bhootika:** Pacifies Kapha and Vata doshas.
 - **Anantamula:** Known for its Tridoshshamak properties.
 - **Kashmari:** Also possesses Tridoshshamak properties.
 - **Parushak:** Specifically pacifies Vata dosha.
 - **Madhuka, Mridwika, Priyal:** All three herbs pacify Vata and Pitta doshas.
 - **Vibhitak:** Pacifies Kapha dosha.
 - **Tila-kalka:** Specifically pacifies Vata dosha.

In conclusion, the Asthanabasti, with its combination of herbs and ingredients, offers a tridoshic balancing effect while mainly targeting the pacification of Vata and Kapha doshas. This holistic approach aims to restore doshic equilibrium, promoting optimal health and well-being.

7.2 The Anuvasanbasti, administered with oil medicated with Madhuka, offers specific therapeutic benefits due to its contents and their actions:[5]

- **Madhuka:** Possesses Vata-pitta shamak properties, indicating its ability to pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas. This herb aids in balancing these doshas within the body, promoting harmony and well-being.

Therefore, the Anuvasanbasti, when combined with Madhuka-medicated oil, primarily serves as a Vata-pitta shamak therapy, aiming to alleviate imbalances related to Vata and Pitta doshas.

7.3 The Anuvasanbasti, enriched with oil medicated with sweet group drugs, offers specific therapeutic benefits due to its contents and their actions:[10]

- **Sweet Group Drugs:** These drugs possess Vata-pitta shamak properties, indicating their ability to pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas. By incorporating these sweet group drugs into the oil, the basti aims to balance these doshas within the body, promoting harmony and well-being.

Therefore, the Anuvasanbasti, when prepared with oil medicated with sweet group drugs, primarily serves as a Vata-pitta shamak therapy, aiming to alleviate imbalances related to Vata and Pitta doshas.

8. BASTI IN GUDA-VEDANA:

In pregnancy, Guda-vedana, characterized by painful conditions in the rectum, often arises due to issues such as parikartika (anal fissure) and piles, commonly caused by constipation. To address these concerns, a specific basti treatment is administered.

This basti therapy is aimed at alleviating Guda-vedana and painful bleeding piles per rectum, which frequently occur during pregnancy due to increased pressure on the uterus and associated constipation. The treatment combines herbs with specific properties to address these symptoms effectively:

- **Vata-Shamak Property:** This property focuses on pacifying Vata dosha, which is often associated with pain and constipation. By relieving Vata, this property helps alleviate pain and discomfort caused by conditions such as anal fissures and piles.
- **Pitta-Shamak Property:** This property is geared towards pacifying Pitta dosha, which can contribute to bleeding. By addressing Pitta dosha, this property helps to stop bleeding associated with conditions like piles.

By incorporating herbs with Vata-shamak and Pitta-shamak properties into the basti, the treatment aims to provide comprehensive relief from Guda-vedana and painful bleeding piles during pregnancy. It addresses the underlying causes of these conditions, including constipation and increased uterine pressure, while also addressing the associated symptoms of pain and bleeding.

8.1 The Anuvasanbasti, combined with Ghrita-manda, offers specific therapeutic benefits due to its content and its action:[11]

- **Ghrita-manda:** Possesses Vata-pitta shamak properties, indicating its ability to pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas. This mixture of ghee and water-based decoction helps to balance these doshas within the body, promoting harmony and well-being.

Therefore, the Anuvasanbasti, when prepared with Ghrita-manda, primarily serves as a Vata-pitta shamak therapy, aiming to alleviate imbalances related to both Vata and Pitta doshas.

9. BASTI FOR FOETAL GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT:

9.1 The Brinhanbasti, administered with Kheer mixed with Salt, offers specific therapeutic benefits due to its content and its action:[12]

- **Kheer:** Possesses Vata-pitta shamak properties, indicating its ability to pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas. Kheer, a preparation made with milk and rice or other grains, provides nourishment and helps in balancing these doshas within the body.
- **Saindhav (Salt):** Known for its Tridoshshamak properties, indicating its ability to balance all three doshas - Vata, Pitta, and Kapha. Salt contributes to the overall balance of the basti preparation by supporting the harmonization of the doshas.

Therefore, the Brinhanbasti, when administered with Kheer mixed with Salt, primarily serves as a Vata-pitta shamak therapy, aiming to alleviate imbalances related to both Vata and Pitta doshas. However, the inclusion of Saindhav also ensures a broader spectrum of doshic balance, making it an effective overall therapy.

9.2 The Anuvasan or Matra basti, containing ghrita medicated with Vidaryadi group drugs, offers specific therapeutic benefits due to its contents and their actions:[13]

- **Vidaryadi Gana:** This group of drugs possesses Vata-pitta shamak properties, indicating their ability to pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas. These herbs, when combined, help in balancing Vata and Pitta doshas within the body, promoting harmony and well-being.
- **Ghrita (Medicated Ghee):** Ghrita itself also possesses Vata-pitta shamak properties, further reinforcing its ability to pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas. It acts as a carrier for the medicinal properties of the herbs and aids in their absorption and assimilation into the body.

Therefore, the Anuvasan or Matra basti, prepared with ghrita medicated with Vidaryadi group drugs, primarily serves as a Vata-pitta shamak therapy. This basti aims to alleviate imbalances related to both Vata and Pitta doshas, providing comprehensive relief and promoting overall well-being.

9.3 The Brinhan Basti, administered with milk, provides therapeutic benefits primarily targeting Vata and Pitta doshas:

- **Milk:** Milk possesses Vata-pitta shamak properties, indicating its ability to pacify both Vata and Pitta doshas. It is known for its nourishing and soothing properties, which help in balancing these doshas within the body.

Therefore, the Brinhan Basti given with milk is considered to be a Vata-pitta shamak therapy, aiming to alleviate imbalances related to both Vata and Pitta doshas, while also providing nourishment and promoting overall well-being.

9.4 The basti administered with milk, ghrita, and sweet drugs is specifically designed to cater to the needs of pregnant women, providing nourishment, promoting anabolic effects, and addressing constipation concerns.[14] Here's an elaboration on its components and their actions:

1. **Milk:** Medicated with Madhura, Sheeta, and Vrunhanaushadha, milk becomes a potent therapeutic medium. It possesses Vata-shamak properties and is used in treating conditions like emaciation and weakness. Milk is rich in essential nutrients like calcium, lactose, butter fat, and moderate amounts of protein. Its anabolic properties aid in maintaining the health of both the mother and the fetus during pregnancy. Moreover, milk is an ideal dietary choice for pregnant women due to its nourishing qualities.
2. **Ghrita:** Ghrita, or medicated ghee, is known for its Vata-pitta shamak properties. It complements the effects of milk, enhancing its therapeutic benefits. Ghrita aids in lubricating the intestines, promoting smooth bowel movements, and preventing constipation, which is crucial for pregnant women to avoid.
3. **Sweet Drugs:** The drugs belonging to the Madhura group are anabolic in nature and contribute to the overall health and well-being of both the mother and the fetus. By incorporating these sweet drugs, the basti aims to support proper growth and development during pregnancy.

By combining milk, ghrita, and sweet drugs, this basti serves as a comprehensive therapy for pregnant women, addressing nutritional needs, promoting anabolic effects, and ensuring proper bowel function. It provides essential nutrients, supports healthy weight gain, and helps in maintaining overall health throughout the pregnancy period.

